

1 Active tectonics and earthquake geology along the Pallatanga Fault, 2 Central Andes of Ecuador

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16 **Keywords: Active tectonics, Earthquake, Pallatanga fault, Andes, Ecuador**

17 Abstract

18 Based on new geological data and the analysis of Digital Elevation Model (DEM), we provide a
19 detailed and comprehensive description of a major active fault system in Ecuador. This work allows
20 estimating new slip rates and large earthquakes parameters (displacement, recurrence) along the ~100
21 km-long section of the continental-scale dextral shear zone that accommodates the extrusion of the
22 North Andean Sliver with respect to the South America continental Plate. We focus on the NE-SW
23 Pallatanga strike-slip fault zone and related contraction features that extend to the north of the
24 previously studied segment, in the Inter-Andean valley.

25 The detailed analysis of the 4m-spatial resolution DEM available for Ecuador allowed mapping a
26 series of lineaments at the regional scale and all along the fault system. Field studies on key areas
27 show geomorphic, valley deflections, aligned and elongated hills of Tertiary or Quaternary
28 sediments, as well as faulted Holocene deposits and even preserved coseismic free-face ruptures in
29 some places. Such morphological anomalies strongly suggest that those landscape scars represent
30 long-living (Holocene to historical times) earthquake faults. Altogether, this new data confirm that
31 very large shallow earthquakes (M~7.5) have been generated along the fault system, probably during
32 multiple segment ruptures. This conclusion is reinforced by the occurrence, during historical times
33 (post 1532 CE) of large earthquakes (1698, 1797 and 1949) in the vicinity of the fault trace during
34 post-Spaniards to modern times, whose effects on environmental and cultural features were reported
35 as catastrophic by historical chronicles.

36 Based on new sample dating of both soils and volcanic series, we infer that the NE-SW dextral
37 Pallatanga fault slips at rates ranging from ~2 to ~6 mm/yr for southern and central strands,
38 respectively. Further north, surface faulting is distributed and the deformation appears to be
39 partitioned between sub-meridian fault-related folds (~2 mm/yr) and NE-SW strike-slip fault(s), like
40 the ~1 mm/yr Pisayambo Fault that ruptured the surface in 2010.

41 All this information offers the opportunity to size the earthquake sources for further seismic hazard
42 analyses.

43 **1 Introduction**

44 Earthquake hazard analyses in continental areas, especially those with sustained seismic activity, are
45 based on fault models supported by detailed studies of active faults (e.g. Field et al., 2014). Those
46 studies classically use fault maps improved after field surveys and paleoseismological data to
47 delineate the active structures and their complexities, the size and recurrence of earthquakes, and the
48 long-term rate of fault slip. Where data is sufficiently reported, it is possible to determine the fault
49 segmentation, i.e. fault sections that behave more or less as independent earthquake sources and that
50 can be treated as such in seismic hazard analyses (DuRoss et al., 2016). In Central Ecuador, the
51 geological knowledge is not achieved yet to support such an approach for hazard purposes, and faults
52 have to be considered as homogenous sources in terms of earthquake production. To date, Beauval et
53 al. (2018) produced the hazard calculation for the entire country, defining a fault model with first-
54 order fault geometries and earthquake parameters. In fact, they only considered two distinct
55 simplified source faults (Pallatanga and Latacunga faults; Fig. 1) between the Western Cordillera
56 and the Eastern Cordillera, with slip rates derived from Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)
57 velocity field (Nocquet et al., 2014). In their model, a massive part of the relative motion between the
58 North-Andean Sliver (NAS) and the South American Plate (SAP) is accommodated by the Pallatanga
59 fault (PF) to which a ~7 mm/yr slip rate is assigned, when field data only provide ~2 to ~5 mm/yr
60 (Baize et al., 2015 and Winter et al., 1993, respectively). This approach is relevant for national scale
61 hazard estimation, but it could be significantly misleading for site-specific approaches nearby the
62 fault sources.

63 The aim of this contribution is to provide an updated active tectonics and earthquake geology
64 knowledge in the Central Ecuador Andes, which could be used in an ad-hoc approach of fault
65 modelling in order to cover the range of earthquake ruptures scenarios (e.g. Chartier et al., 2019). We
66 focused on a 100 km-long and 20 km-wide area covering a section of the fault zone that delineates
67 the eastern margin of the NNE-moving North-Andean Sliver (NAS), west of the South American
68 Plate (SAP) (Fig. 1) and which has been defined as the Chingual Cosanga Pallatanga Puna Fault
69 System (CCPP; Alvarado et al., 2016; Nocquet et al., 2014; Yepes et al., 2016) between Colombia to
70 the Pacific Ocean. The new evidences of earthquakes ruptures are supported by morphological and
71 geological observations performed during five field campaigns around the Riobamba region (Central
72 Ecuador; Fig. 1). In the frame of the geodynamics and active tectonics of the Northern Andes of
73 Ecuador, we present our major findings based on morphological analysis of a 4m-high resolution
74 DEM and field investigations. We propose a revised fault map and derive our observations in terms
75 of slip rates (dislocation of dated features or separation of landscape features), earthquake
76 recurrences and magnitudes, which are crucial parameters of geological-based seismic hazard
77 analyses. Here, we will particularly focus on the Riobamba area (R), the Igualata-Huisla volcanoes
78 (IH), the Pisayambo region (P) and the Latacunga zone (L).

79 **2 General background**

80 2.1 Crustal structure

81 Imaging the crust in Ecuador has been challenging for years. A new model has been recently
 82 proposed for the whole country (Araujo, 2016; Font et al., 2013; Vaca et al., 2019), and allowed
 83 relocation of earthquake events, including at depth. Based on an inversion of arrival times of more
 84 than 45,000 seismic events spanning more than 20 years of seismicity, Araujo (2016) proposes a new
 85 seismic tomography imaging the subducted slab and the overriding crust. The Andean Cordilleras are
 86 characterized by an over-thickened crust above a Moho discontinuity that is imaged between 50 and
 87 60 km deep. The intense crustal seismic activity in the last 20 years is focused around the active
 88 volcanoes, as well as the active tectonic structures such as the Quito-Latacunga fault-related fold
 89 (QLF) system and the CCPP shear zone (Fig. 1). This seismicity is clustered in the first 30 km
 90 according to Araujo (2016) and, consistently, the analysis of seismicity depth from the Beauval et al.
 91 (2013) catalogue document, 90% of the seismicity surrounding the PF and the QLF (in a 20 km
 92 radius) is located between 0 and 30 km deep.

93 2.2 Geodynamical setting

94 Seismotectonic activity in Ecuador is dominated by the subduction of the Nazca plate below the
 95 South American plate. Subduction-related megathrust earthquakes, such as the April 2016 M7.8
 96 Pedernales event, constitute the most frequent and significant contribution to the seismic hazard, in
 97 terms of expected seismic ground motion. However, severe shallow and crustal earthquakes jolted
 98 and destroyed large cities of Ecuador around the CCPP, like in the Riobamba region in 1694, 1797
 99 and 1949, or within the NAS in the Inter-Andean Valley (IAV), like in 1868 near Ibarra (Beauval et
 100 al., 2010).

101 The CCPP Fault System accommodates the relative displacement between the NAS and the SAP. It
 102 may have started after 3 Ma according to offshore data in the Guayaquil Gulf (Deniaud et al., 1999;
 103 Jean François Dumont et al., 2005a, 2005b; Witt et al., 2006a), cutting obliquely across the accreted
 104 terranes and related N-S structures of the Ecuadorian Andes (Alvarado et al., 2016). The transpressive
 105 deformation regime that accompanies this north-eastward motion of NAS along the CCPP. The
 106 obliquity between the Nazca Plate and the SAP convergence vector (6 cm/yr according to Kendrick
 107 et al., 2003) and the trench direction is thought to be the reason of the deformation partitioning and
 108 shearing along the CCPP (Alvarado et al., 2016). GNSS measurements show that this wide and large
 109 shear zone accommodates around 7-9 mm/yr between the North Andean Sliver and the stable South
 110 America Plate (Nocquet et al., 2014b). In their tectonic model, Alvarado et al. (2016) describe a
 111 Quito-Latacunga Microblock in the IAV with diffuse active faults and seismic activity west of the
 112 merging of the NNE-SSW-striking Pallatanga fault (PF) and N-S striking Cosanga fault (CF; Figure
 113 1).

114 Vaca et al. (2019) provide new focal mechanisms of earthquakes within the 2009-2015 time span,
 115 based on seismic velocity structure and data from the Ecuadorian broadband seismic network. In the
 116 area comprised between Pallatanga and the Pisayambo area, focal mechanisms of low magnitude
 117 events cover a range of dextral and thrust motions. This transpressive regime deduced from
 118 earthquakes is coherent with the mean horizontal strain tensor that they determined from GPS
 119 velocity field. In their calculation, the principal compressional stress is N^o70E oriented, in agreement
 120 with long-term (Pleistocene-Holocene) fault kinematics (Alvarado et al., 2016).

121 2.3 Bedrock geology

122 The study area is part of the Ecuadorian Andes that extends north-south between the coast and the
 123 Amazon lowlands. From west to east, it covers various geological units: (1) the Western Cordillera
 124 that corresponds to oceanic terranes and its related sediments, which have been accreted during
 125 phases of Caribbean Plateau and SAP convergence (Cretaceous-Eocene; Hughes and Pilatasig, 2002;
 126 Jaillard et al., 2009; Pindell and Kennan, 2009; Vallejo et al., 2006); (2) a narrow (max. 30 km) and
 127 300 km long NS structural depression (2,000 to 3,000 m of elevation (IAV) where part of the
 128 volcanic arc is lying and where Miocene to Holocene deposits are accumulated (Bablon et al., 2019;
 129 Hall et al., 2008; Jaillard et al., 2009), and (3) the Real Cordillera, culminating at ~4,500 m a.s.l, a
 130 sequence of Paleozoic to Cretaceous basement rocks of the SAP (Aspden and Litherland, 1992;
 131 Spikings and Crowhurst, 2004). These large-scale structural units are obliquely cut by the CCPP,
 132 which initiates in the Guayaquil Gulf and the coastal plain, penetrates the Western Cordillera, then
 133 cuts the IAV and the Cordillera Real to finally merge the CF (Figure 1).

134 **2.4 Quaternary environment**

135 The various active and potentially active volcanic centers of Central Ecuador are mainly andesitic.
 136 Most of them are located along the margins of the IAV, either on the Western one (Chimborazo,
 137 Iliniza, Guagua Pichincha) or the Eastern one (Tungurahua, Cotopaxi Antisana, Cayambe). Few are
 138 lying within the IAV (Iguayata, Huisla, Imbabura).

139 The highest areas of the Andes, including volcanic peaks, have hosted ice glaciers during the
 140 Quaternary. During the Late Glacial Maximum roughly between 33 and 14 ka (e.g., Clapperton,
 141 1990), the large expansion of the glaciers towards the valleys left moraines down to elevation of
 142 3600 m above sea level. During the very late cold phase (Younger Dryas, around 10-12 ka), the
 143 glaciers did not reach these relative low elevations and preserved moraines are found at around
 144 ~4000 m (Samaniego et al., 2012). During the Holocene, thick organic soils, referred as andisols, have
 145 developed.

146 **3 Methods**

147 The active shallow structures of concern have been first investigated as soon as the 1990's (e.g.
 148 Lavenu et al., 1995; Soulas et al., 1991; Winter et al., 1993). These pioneer studies came out with
 149 significant slip rates (> 1 mm/yr), showing up that they pose a significant seismic hazard. During the
 150 last decade, our franco-ecuadorian team ("*Laboratoire Mixte International Séismes et Volcans des*
 151 *Andes du Nord*", see <http://lmi.igeppn.edu.ec/>) launched new research that combine seismology,
 152 geodesy and geology (e.g. Alvarado et al., 2016, 2014; Baize et al., 2015; Champenois et al., 2017,
 153 2014; Font et al., 2013; Nocquet et al., 2016, 2014) and consolidated the seismotectonic model
 154 (Yepes et al., 2016) at the whole country scale.

155 In this paper, we present the results of a part of this broad project, after developing geomorphological
 156 and geological data from DEM analysis and field observations. This work provides an accurate
 157 arrangement of active faults and in places yields hints on slip rate values. Starting from the
 158 neotectonic map (Alvarado, 2012), we developed our efforts in the area covering the fault zone
 159 between 0.8°S and 1.8°S along a 40 km-wide and NE-SW-striking band (figure 3), where the tectonic
 160 map is almost 'blank' (R, IH, P sectors; Figure 1), and where strain is suspected to split between both
 161 dominantly NE-SW to NNE-SSW strike-slip strands and N-S compressional fault-related folds. The
 162 study area extends between the cities of Pallatanga to the South and Latacunga to the North. In the
 163 Ecuadorian Andes, mapping of active faults and folds is a difficult task because of morphoclimatic
 164 conditions, especially at low elevations (below c. 2500 m a.s.l.), where steep slopes and rainfall

165 favour dense forest and gravitational instability. At high elevation, where farming is absent (>3800m
 166 a.s.l.), morphologic features are often well preserved and can be revealed by DEM and field analyses,
 167 but their accessibility can be limited because of rare tracks and toughness of hiking over large
 168 distances at high elevations. To obtain the most complete picture over the 1000 km² zone, we
 169 performed the morphotectonic analysis of a 4-m-pixel-resolution Digital Elevation Model (Proyecto
 170 SIGTIERRAS, www.sigtierras.gob.ec) draped over the geological maps (Longo and Baldock, 1982).
 171 Field data were acquired during five two-week campaigns between 2009 and 2016 at key areas.

172 Like in classical preliminary analyses, we looked for morphological features, their alignment and
 173 continuity of lineaments to delineate portions of faults. The fault portions could be traced and
 174 characterized thanks to a wide panel of features that constitute the classic landform assemblage of
 175 active strike-slip faults (McCalpin, 2009), such as pressure or shutter ridges, sag-ponds, terrace risers
 176 or entrenched thalweg deflections, cumulative scarps that cause vertical shifts of regular surfaces
 177 (lava flows, alluvial terraces, hillslopes, etc...), and free-face scarps.

178 Potential active fault portions were defined based on the continuity, proximity and coherence of the
 179 morphological clues, which are, within the IAV, developed in (mostly) volcanic products mplaced
 180 during the last 600 kyr (Bablon et al., 2019) accumulated in this high-elevation and intra-
 181 mountainous basin. During the field campaigns, we could check that most of such lineaments were
 182 associated with brittle structures in volcanic formations. As an iconic case, we provide the hillshade
 183 image of the DEM in the area of the 2009 trenches which revealed the correlation between
 184 morphologic features and active faulting (Baize et al., 2015) (Figure 2). Other examples are described
 185 hereafter. We implicitly assume that the Quaternary era is the appropriate reference time frame to
 186 describe and analyse properly the active tectonics of the CCPP fault system in an earthquake hazard
 187 perspective.

188 **4 Results**

189 Five sectors were investigated along the PF and its transition toward both the CF and the QLF, in
 190 terms of long-term (Quaternary) and recent (Holocene to historical earthquake surface ruptures)
 191 activity. Those are Rumipamba (R), Riobamba and Igualata / Huisla volcanoes, as well as the Patate
 192 river valley (IH), Laguna Pisayambo (P) and Salcedo/Latacunga (L) (Figures 1 and 3). Our new
 193 mapping in IH area completes and improves those of Baize et al. (2015) and Champenois et al.
 194 (2017) on the Rumipamba and Pisayambo areas, respectively. In Supplementary material, we provide
 195 five maps featuring the fault strands layered over the 4 m spatial resolution DEM (Figures S6 to
 196 S11).

197 **4.1 From Pallatanga to Riobamba**

198 All along the first 75 kilometres of the fault zone in the Western Cordillera, it is possible to map
 199 pervasive NE-SW structural lineaments stepping one after the other, defining a rather simple albeit
 200 large and well-defined fault trace (Alvarado et al., 2016b) (Figures 3 and S1). While gaining in
 201 elevation to the north from the coastal flat zone, morpho-tectonic features are still very clear. The
 202 southernmost trace of our detailed investigation, south of Pallatanga city, is underlined by a series of
 203 right-stepping 2-to-5 km long lineaments with east-facing large scale scarps (Figure S1). North of the
 204 city and its wide topographic depression, a continuous trace defines a quite continuous fault section,
 205 and the 4 m DEM starts to highlight continuous clues of strike-slip faulting north to the Rumipamba
 206 area (Figure S2). Note that the area also encompasses remarkable signs of deep-seated gravitational
 207 deformations at the range crests and many landslide scars (Figure 3). The Rumipamba area reveals

208 the best morphologic features of active strike-slip faulting along the PF (Figure 2 and pictures 2009-1
 209 to 2009-16 & 17, 2010-18 to 2010-19-2 in Supplementary material). This is where the first active
 210 tectonics investigations were engaged in Central Ecuador, evidencing horizontally and vertically
 211 displaced crests and thalwegs, sagponds (Winter et al., 1993), and traces of paleoearthquakes (Baize
 212 et al., 2015). Further north, while entering the IAV, the unique and NE-SW fault trace in Rumipamba
 213 zone intersects volcanic and volcano-sedimentary Quaternary deposits (figure 3), and splits into a
 214 series of lineaments striking between WSW-ENE and NNE-SSW. Markers suggesting a strike-slip
 215 motion encompass pressure ridges, displaced creeks (pictures 2010-56 and 2010-63-1 & 2,
 216 Supplementary material), and dislocated volcanic deposits within a 2 km-wide band (pictures 2015-
 217 56-1 & 2, Supplementary material). The traces of fault lines have slightly been revised after Baize et
 218 al. (2015) study, to account for later observations (Figures 3 and S2).

219 **4.2 The Iqualata volcano area**

220 Newly evidenced and striking fault strands are mapped across the Iqualata edifice, from its southwest
 221 foothills (Figure 4 and pictures 2015-54 to 2015-65-2 in Suppl. Mat.) to its summit part (Figures 5
 222 and 6; pictures 2015-2 to 13), and across the northeast slope to the Huisla volcano area (Figures 7
 223 and 8; picture 2015-41 in Suppl. Mat.). When looking carefully at the hummocky surface of the
 224 Chimborazo-related Debris Avalanche Deposits (DAD), south the Iqualata volcano and nearby San
 225 Andres village, some features present aligned-to-fault strikes, as well as vertical or lateral
 226 separations. It is for instance possible to document a NE-SW ridge, perpendicular to the DAD flow,
 227 along which creeks and valley slopes incised in the DAD are dextrally deflected (e.g. labels A and B,
 228 figure 4) between 60 and 160 m. The Guano lava flow (figure 4), which is embedded in the DAD-
 229 incised San Andres valley, is bumped and show apparent vertical and lateral separation in San
 230 Andres village. Interestingly, the general course of the deflected creek (at label A, figure 4) presents a
 231 smaller-scale deflection of about 10 meters nearby a proof of brittle deformation in post-VAD sands
 232 and soils. We speculate that this latter 10 m offset could be due to the most recent earthquake surface
 233 rupture (see hereafter the observations on top of the Iqualata volcano). At that specific site, the walls
 234 of a mill were damaged (see picture 2015-54 in Supplementary material). We dated charcoal samples
 235 embedded in the mortar of the repairs at 145 ± 30 and 185 ± 30 BP, suggesting that the mill has
 236 potentially been damaged then fixed after the M_{~7-7.5} 1694 or 1797 earthquakes, whose epicentres
 237 were close (Beauval et al., 2010).

238 Along the southwestern slopes of Iqualata volcano, north of San Andres, we could trace a series of
 239 compelling evidences with cumulative dextral offsets of landscape features (horizontal: 20-50 m;
 240 vertical: 5-10 m), individual scarplets (vertical: 1 m) and faulted soils (label C, figure 4), as described
 241 in the Supplementary material (pictures 2015-64-1 to 2015-65-2). The best indication of historical
 242 surface faulting is observed in the Iqualata volcano summit part (figure 5), with NE-SW counter-
 243 slope scarps displacing valley floors, free-face scarps and fresh en-echelon fractures (figure 6 and
 244 pictures 2015-2 to 2015-13 in Suppl. material). The occurrence of five abandoned erosional features
 245 (called “CH” on figure 6) in the downthrown block (‘a’ to ‘e’ in Figure 6) matching the same feature
 246 on the uplifted block is a compelling mark of the long-term activity and probably the succession of
 247 five displacement events. The fault trace can be mapped up to the northern Iqualata volcano slope,
 248 displacing the Late Pleistocene moraine deposits, terrace risers, and Holocene marsh deposits (Figure
 249 5 and pictures 2016-7 and 2016-3&7&9 in Suppl. material). The north-east continuation of active
 250 faulting of this portion could not be clearly documented in the field in correspondence to DEM-
 251 mapped lineaments, except across the Mulmul volcano (145-175 kyr; Bablon et al., 2019; Figure 8).

252 The overall shape of the Iguatala volcano testifies the long-term activity of the fault, which has
 253 caused the formation of large, deep and cross-cutting valley from SW to NE (figure 7). When
 254 roughly reconstructing the geometry of the edifice on each side of the fault zone (red strands on
 255 Figure 7), we come out with an approximate right-lateral separation of 1500 m of SW base and of
 256 2100 m of NE base, assuming a symmetrical and roughly cylindrical shape.

257 **4.3 A step-over to Huisla volcano fault portion**

258 North of the best-documented evidences on the Iguatala volcano, we report clues of cumulative fault
 259 displacement across Huisla volcano (500-600 ka, Bablon et al., 2019) beyond a ~5 km step-over.
 260 There, the Huisla volcano is dislocated by a NE-SW fault section. This fault throws down the south-
 261 eastern part of the volcano (figure 8). The morphology of the Huisla strato-volcano is characterized
 262 by a collapse amphitheatre resulting from a large and sudden collapse of its southeastern flank
 263 between 215 and 180 kyr (Bablon et al., 2019). Huisla and related avalanche have been subsequently
 264 faulted during the Pleistocene (and Holocene?). The fault segment is revealed along its course to the
 265 NE down to the Patate River valley at several places (figure 8), with one creek incised within the
 266 DAD with a significant (≈ 60 m) right-lateral component, for instance (label A, figure 8 and picture
 267 2015-26&27, Supplementary material). On the Patate River western slope, a road-cut of the new
 268 Pelileo-Riobamba highway offers massive outcrops with many gravitational and tectonic deformation
 269 features. In one of these, we could document a Pleistocene NE-SW strike-slip shear plane between
 270 the Huisla VAD and a series of non-dated deposits with inter-stratified colluvial and volcanic fall
 271 layers (figure 8b). One can notice that the older layers are affected by soft-sediment deformation,
 272 including folds, slumps and intra-formational faults. Downslope, we speculate that the damming of a
 273 perched NW-SE short valley could be due to a “positive” vertical deformation during right-lateral
 274 faulting (label B, figure 8 and pictures 2015-33-3&4). The northernmost Huisla fault segment
 275 crosscuts the Patate valley to reach the western flanks of the Eastern Cordillera, approaching a length
 276 of about ~20 km. In that area, it is possible to map (Figure 3 and Figure S10) several short and
 277 discontinuous N-S to NE-SW linear morphological features with some dextral deflection evidences
 278 (Suppl. Material: pictures 2016-21, 27, 30, 32, 35) or fault expression in Quaternary deposits (Suppl.
 279 Material: pictures 2016-16 and 36). Actually, the fault seems to scatter amidst this buttress of
 280 Western Cordillera basement and finally appears to be deviated to the north, depicting a $>30^\circ$ bend
 281 (Z label). Note that this area includes the epicentral area of the 1949 Pelileo earthquake that caused
 282 many landslides and other secondary effects during shaking (Semanante, 1950).

283 **4.4 The Laguna Pisayambo area and the Pisayambo fault**

284 It was not possible to reach the high mountain area in the Llanganates National Park between
 285 waypoints 2016-20 and 2014-33 (Figure S10 in Suppl. Material) because of high elevation, steep
 286 relief and absence of tracks. There is a lack of clear lineament on the DEM between the
 287 aforementioned neotectonic clues and the NE-SW active Laguna Pisayambo fault mapped and
 288 observed close to the Angahuana volcano (Figure S10), raising the possibility of a 15 km-wide active
 289 fault gap (figure 3). Interestingly, this fault ruptured up to the surface in 2010 during a moderate
 290 earthquake ($M \sim 5$) (Champenois et al., 2017), and this historical surface rupture exactly sticks to a
 291 cumulative fault that dextrally displaces Pleistocene moraines of about ≈ 15 meters and disrupts
 292 Holocene soils (Figure 9b and 9c; pictures 2014-18-1 and 2014-32 in Suppl. Material). A
 293 stratigraphic section in a hand-made trench allowed the check of the 2010 and syn-andisol
 294 development (Holocene) activity of the fault, during the last 8 ky (See Figure S4 in Champenois et
 295 al., 2017 and picture 2014-34, Suppl. Material). Further north-east, several rather short lineaments
 296 (13 and 26 km) come one after the other separated by gaps or step-overs. These *a priori* strike-slip

301 segments (they are grouped into the Pisayambo Fault zone) merge the Andean east-verging Cosanga
 302 thrust (Alvarado et al., 2016b). The fault segments strike around N30°-N50°E, and are parallel but
 303 not coincident with the Pucara fault defined several km further south (Alvarado, 2012).

300 **4.5 Salcedo-Latacunga Folds**

301 Turning back south to the Pelileo area, a striking point in the active fault map of the region is the
 302 north-south system of fault-related folds that arises north of the aforementioned basement buttress.
 303 Those NS structures, bounding the Inter-Andean depression north of the CCPP system, are
 304 kinematically consistent with this right-lateral fault system (Lavenue et al., 1995). The southernmost
 305 signs of folding in Quaternary deposits crop out in an area where they imbricate intimately with NE-
 306 SW scarps and lineaments (Figure S10 in Suppl. Material), a similar pattern as proposed by Fiorini
 307 and Tibaldi (2012) to the north in the Cotopaxi volcano region. The IAV is morphologically marked
 308 by flat surfaces, with rivers (e.g. Rio Patate) deeply incised in loose volcano-sedimentary sediments.
 309 Both DEM analysis and field observations underline the occurrence of many NS flexures, tilted
 310 surfaces and layers, elongated ridges, sometimes damming the drainage network (Laguna de Yambo,
 311 see pictures 2015-01 and 2016-55 in Suppl. Material), and even reverse faults (Figure 10 and picture
 312 2016-53 in Suppl. Material). In map view, the general pattern of fault-related fold lines steps with a
 313 leftward en-echelon-like pattern toward the North. We could not evidence any lateral component of
 314 deformation in the area covered by the Figure 10 map. The morphological imprint of those
 315 compressive structures vanishes to the north and we assume that there is a significant gap in sub-
 316 surface faulting pattern. However, it is worth mentioning that Fiorini and Tibaldi (2012) report similar
 317 NS folds 15 km northward, close to the Cotopaxi volcano, which could then connect to the QLF.

318 The current activity of the N-S structures is strongly supported by the SAR data that were processed
 319 and presented by (Champenois et al., 2014). Those authors used results from Advanced Synthetic
 320 Aperture Radar (ASAR) data provided by the Envisat satellite (C-band with a 5.6 cm wavelength; 23
 321 ENVISAT SAR data; Ascending pass). They determine the surface deformation rate between 2003
 322 and 2009, using the Persistent Scatters InSAR (PSI) technique to perform time series analysis of
 323 ground deformation. The Figure 11 is a zoom out of the Figure 2 in Champenois et al. (2014),
 324 showing the deformation in the Tungurahua volcano region. One can easily see that the InSAR-PS
 325 map also clearly depicts differential motion rates in the Line-of-Sight (LOS) across the IAV and its
 326 rims (Figure 11). Basically, positive LOS velocities depict pixels that move up (a lot) and west (a
 327 few), whereas negative values represent relative subsiding (or moving eastward) pixels. On Figure
 328 11, we observe from west to east along the P1 profile a gentle and undulating decrease in the Line-
 329 Of-Sight displacement rate of about ~ 2 mm/yr over 30 km. We suggest that this gentle eastward
 330 decreasing pattern of uplift may be due to the interseismic loading due to the subduction, as
 331 demonstrated by GNSS (Nocquet et al., 2014b). This slope is then disrupted by a sharper gradient in
 332 displacement rate across a ~2-km narrow band, in the area where the western structure bounding the
 333 IAV is mapped (Alvarado, 2012). Another step is found to the East, at the eastern edge of the IAV
 334 and, once again, it matches with the location of a mapped active structure. Because of their proximity
 335 in the study area, we speculate that there could be a structural linkage at depth between those NS
 336 fault-related folds and the strike-slip fault system located some km to the south. Assuming this
 337 relationship, there would be a conservation of strain across the area, accommodating the relative
 338 motion between NAS v SAP.

339 **5 Analysis**

340 **5.1 Structural complexity**

341 The new fault map depicts a series of fault sections including discontinuities, branching or sub-
 342 parallel strands, step-overs (max. 5 km), km-scale gaps or bends. Such complexities are rather
 343 common along active strike-slip fault systems within which earthquake ruptures can propagate.
 344 However, despite this complexity, individual fault portions do not show any dramatic internal
 345 changes, except for the area between the Huisla volcano and the eastern cordillera area where bends
 346 exceed 25°. The short surface distance (3-5 km) between the fault-related folds and the imbrication of
 347 compressional and strike-slip features in the Pelileo area suggest that there could be a structural
 348 relationship at depth between the two families of faults. Considering that the complete fault network
 349 is related to the same geodynamic input (i.e. the NAS motion to the NNE with respect to SAP), this
 350 interaction would imply a conservation of slip rates from south to north, across the fault network.

351 5.2 Slip rates

352 Deflected morphological features and offset Quaternary formations allow inferring slip rate
 353 information. The fault zones cut a large panel of rocks, including Paleozoic basement (Eastern
 354 Cordillera) and Cretaceous/Tertiary volcanic rocks from the Western Cordillera terranes, but also
 355 recently dated Pleistocene/Holocene volcanic units, glacial deposits and thick Holocene andisols.
 356 During the field campaigns, we pointed out several spots where the amount of displacement of
 357 relatively recent deposits or the separation of landforms could be estimated.

358 The oldest K-Ar age obtained for Igualata volcano (376 ± 10 ka; Bablon et al., 2019) is interpreted as
 359 a minimum age for this edifice. This age provides a very long-term estimation of maximum slip rate
 360 for the northernmost segment of the Pallatanga fault. We estimate this slip rate based on the dextral
 361 apparent horizontal separation of the hinge line marking the base of the edifice. This estimation is
 362 highly uncertain because of our low ability to define precisely this piercing line (toe of the volcano
 363 slope). The southern flank toe appears to be offset between 900 and ~1500 m (depending on the
 364 projection of the piercing lines applied to the wide fault zone), whereas the northern slope appears to
 365 be massively disrupted (~2100 m, even 2500 m when considering an alternative option for projecting
 366 the slope toes). Considering the oldest age of this edifice, the resulting maximum and long-term slip
 367 rate range from 2.4-4 mm/yr (southern slope) to 5.6-6.6 mm/yr (northern slope). In addition, we
 368 assume that the Pallatanga fault already had an impact on morphology when the lava flow dated at
 369 237 ± 9 kyr (Bablon et al., 2019) have been emplaced in the southern fault-controlled valley.

370 On the same segment, south-west of Igualata volcano, the fault cuts the Guano valley, as well as the
 371 massive volcanic avalanche deposit (DAD) which was deposited during the catastrophic collapse of
 372 the Chimborazo edifice between 42 and 62 ± 4 kyr, according to the age of overlying tephra fallout
 373 deposits (Samaniego et al., 2012) and underlying lava flow (Bablon et al., 2019), respectively. The
 374 drainage incised in this massive volcanic package is dextrally offset, and the two spots are used to
 375 evaluate the cumulative slip. At site A (Figure 4), the drainage is offset by 60 to 120 m, depending on
 376 the chosen projection of upstream piercing line (incised channel or northern valley slope), whereas
 377 the southern slope of Guano valley (site B; Figure 4) is displaced between 60 to 90 m (depending on
 378 the projection of used piercing line, i.e. base of slope). Assuming that the drainage has started to
 379 incise after the DAD emplacement, this provides a slip rate range value between 1-2.7 mm/yr (site A)
 380 to 1-2 mm/yr (site B). This bracket represents a minimum value, because the offset drainage could be
 381 younger, for instance dating only back to the Holocene onset (12 kyr), then slip rate could reach an
 382 unlikely value of ~10 mm/yr. Otherwise, the same fault strand deforms the 4 ± 2 Guano lava flow
 383 (Bablon et al., 2019) in San Andres. The flat upper surface of this lava flow is clearly bumped along
 384 a tiny linear ridge in continuation of the fault. However, the lateral offset of the lava flow edge
 385 cannot be inferred from the DEM analysis. Note that other oblique strand has been detected by Baize

386 et al. (2015) to the east, which deflects VAD landscape features by ~110 m. Summing up these two
 387 segments, a value of 3.6-4 mm/yr seems to best fit the data at this fault section, following the various
 388 hypotheses.

389 Along the slopes of the deep incision in the Igualata volcano summit area (~3800-3900 m a.s.l.), the
 390 small-scale incision (“CH”), still active today, is offset of 73 ± 5 meters (Figure 6). Although we do
 391 not know the age of this incision feature, we suggest that it could have been formed after the retreat
 392 of glaciers that filled the valley down to 3600 m asl. during the Last Glacial Maximum (30 ± 3 to ~14
 393 kyr (Samaniego et al., 2012). Consequently, the minimum slip rate there may then range between 2.1
 394 mm/yr (68 m in 33 kyr) to 5.6 mm/yr (78 m in 14 kyr).

395 In Rumipamba, Winter et al. (1993) then Baize et al. (2015) estimated, based on the cumulative
 396 offset of **Holocene** morphological features and successive vertical displacements of **late Holocene**
 397 soils, that the apparent and mean slip rate ranges between 2.9-4.6 mm/yr and 2.5 mm/yr, respectively.
 398 We provide an updated analysis of slip rate (2.1 mm/yr) based on paleoearthquake record in the
 399 following section. Note that, accounting for the 41.5 m offset measured by Winter et al. (1993) on
 400 landscape features, and revising their ‘post-glacial’ age from 10-13 kyr of those authors to 30-14 kyr
 401 (Samaniego et al., 2012), we come out with a very consistent mean slip rate values determined from
 402 large-scale morphological features’ offset and displaced soils (1.4-3 mm/yr range).

403 The Huisla segment is poorly documented. The only indication is a 60 m deflection of a drainage
 404 incision in the Huisla DAD, overlooked with DEM and checked in the field. The only temporal
 405 constrain available is the 215-180 kyr age of the Huisla-related DAD (Bablon et al., 2019), providing
 406 a minimal slip rate of 0.3 mm/yr that does not seem realistic. Assuming that the drainage started to
 407 incise at the beginning of the Holocene, a speculative upper bound value 4 mm/yr is determined. The
 408 drainage deflection is located on the same lineament as the recent rupture visible in the road cut 5 km
 409 to the north-east (Figure 8b).

410 In Pisayambo area, we could map in different places the horizontal offset of moraines, between 15
 411 and 20 meters. Considering their elevation (~3700 m), these moraines could be associated with the
 412 LGM (33 to 14 kyr) by analogy to the Chimborazo volcano flanks (Samaniego et al., 2012). These
 413 values would end up with a relatively low slip rate ranging between 0.45 and 1.4 mm/yr for the
 414 Pisayambo Fault.

415 Concerning the NS compressive structures, the mean Plio-Quaternary shortening rate across the IAV
 416 has been previously estimated around 1.4 mm/yr (Lavenue et al., 1995), including both the N-S
 417 structures that bound the IAV to the west and to the east. More recently, (Fiorini and Tibaldi, 2012)
 418 stated that slip rates along the thrust faults described are unknown, but provide an estimate of less
 419 than 1 mm/yr along each fault. We hereafter propose another evaluation based on InSAR data
 420 (Champenois et al., 2014) presented above. On Figure 11, we observe along the P1 profile that the
 421 first Line-Of-Sight displacement rate associated with the western border of IAV is about ~1 mm/yr
 422 over ~2-km narrow band in the area. The second LOS displacement rate step found to the East at the
 423 eastern margin of IAV is around ~-1.8 mm/yr and the sense of LOS displacement is consistent with a
 424 relative uplift of the eastern cordillera. Assuming that those border faults are reverse and that the slip
 425 vector is for both faults parallel to the LOS, we can easily estimate their geodetic slip rates. Although
 426 the dips of these two faults are not well constrained, we assign 50° values by analogy with the Quito
 427 reverse fault, whereas the LOS is dipping by $\sim 70^\circ$. When projecting the LOS onto the two fault
 428 planes, we end up with actual slip rates of **1.7 mm/yr and 0.5 mm/yr** for the Eastern and Western
 429 Boundary Faults, respectively. Those reverse faults slip rates are much lower than the one determined

430 for the Quito Fault (3 to 5 mm/yr) in the same large tectonic block (QLB; Alvarado et al., 2014), a
 431 fault that is now recognized to absorb a portion of shallow creep in its central part (Marinière et al.,
 432 2020).

433 The lower and upper bound values of slip rate are summarized in Table 1.

434 **5.3 Earthquake surface ruptures and their recurrence**

435 We recompiled the original radiocarbon ages obtained in Baize et al. (2015) trench, together with the
 436 measured vertical offsets. Soil samples ^{14}C ages are calibrated with OxCal software (Bronk Ramsey,
 437 2009), using the IntCal13 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2013) to infer the possible range of paleo-
 438 earthquake dates. We provide details of this analysis in Supplementary material. The geological
 439 interpretation of the trench T2, located a few tens of meters south of the trench visible on Figure 2,
 440 led to propose a series of 4 paleoearthquakes, i.e. a recording of 3 complete earthquake cycles
 441 bracketed by E4, E3, E2 and E1 within the last ~8000 years. Based on the calibrated ages, we come
 442 out with the most probable following dates: E4=-4250, E3=-2400, E3=+400 and an historical
 443 earthquake (post +1000; Figure 12). We supposed this last event to be the 1797 Riobamba
 444 earthquake, which seems to be the best candidate for this rupture, because of the vicinity of its
 445 epicentral location. However, we cannot completely rule out the M~7.2 1698 event or even the M6.8
 446 1949 Pelileo earthquake. Accounting for the maximum, mean and minimum values of slip vector, i.e.
 447 20° , 11.5° and 6° (Winter et al., 1993; Baize et al., 2015), the individual net slip during E1 to E4
 448 events range between 2 and 8.6 m, corresponding to moment magnitudes ranging between 7.3 and
 449 7.9 for strike-slip earthquakes (Wells and Coppersmith, 1994). Figure 12 illustrates the slip versus
 450 time history that can be inferred from the trench result. Over the 3 earthquake cycles, the cumulative
 451 fault displacement is between 7.3, 12.5 and 23 m, respectively slip vectors of 20° , 11.5° and 6° ,
 452 ranging the short-term (last 6000 years) slip rate between 1.2 and 3 mm/yr. We stress that the
 453 prolongation of slip rate line to the old ages in the trench (black dashed lines) intersects the “0” slip
 454 value, close to the oldest soil sampled a few cm above the bottom of the Holocene series. This
 455 strongly suggests that this soil was developed promptly after a morphogenic earthquake that created
 456 space for sediment accumulation.

457 On top of the ~350 ka old Igualata volcano, the five successive dextral displacements of “CH” are
 458 between 7 and 18 m, ending up with a cumulative right-lateral offset of ~73 m. The cumulative
 459 vertical component is around 4 meters (figure 4). Assuming that those evidences are caused by
 460 surface-rupturing morphogenic earthquakes, we stress that the values are in the order of the highest
 461 offsets ever inferred for single events (>15 m), such as those due to the M~8 Wairarapa, New
 462 Zealand, earthquake in 1855 (Rodgers and Little, 2006) or the M7.6 Chi Chi, Taiwan, earthquake in
 463 2001 (Lin et al., 2001), but massively larger than those ever measured recently such as the 8 - 9 m on
 464 the 2002 M7.9 Denali, Alaska, rupture (Haeussler et al., 2004), on the 2001 M7.8 Kokoxili, China,
 465 rupture (Klinger et al., 2005), the 2008 M7.9 Wenchuan, China, rupture (Yu et al., 2010), or even the
 466 12 m on the 2016 M7.8 Kaikoura rupture in New Zealand (Kearse et al., 2018; Langridge et al.,
 467 2018). Based on this worldwide catalogue, we question that the Igualata proofs of earthquake
 468 ruptures could correspond to a series of five single event offsets and, therefore, we suggest that the
 469 time required to generate this CH feature is longer than recurrence of large earthquakes, i.e. 1500 to
 470 3000 years if we refer to the Rumipamba trench.

471 Along the Pisayambo section (north-east of Pelileo city) of the fault system, a magnitude 5
 472 earthquake caused a surface rupture along a 9 km long fault with pure right-lateral surface
 473 displacements (maximum ~30 cm according to field observations, ~40 cm according to InSAR

474 results). The hand-made trench, as presented in the Supporting information of Champenois et al.
 475 (2017), shows the main fault zone between the (presumably) Pleistocene moraine and the organic soil
 476 with a reactivation (opening) during the 2010 event. This section, as well as the general
 477 geomorphology (see picture 2014-18-1, in Supplementary material), suggest the occurrence of two
 478 surface-rupturing events by the alignments of pebbles within the soil, one between -2500 and -1070
 479 cal B.C, and the other between -840 and -340 cal B.C. However, the sedimentary signal is too weak
 480 to go further and estimate vertical separation, for instance.

481 **6 Discussion**

482 We estimate that multiple-segment ruptures could occur along the Pallatanga fault system. Biasi and
 483 Wesnousky (2017, 2016), based on a worldwide historical database, propose that the likelihood of
 484 rupture propagation is linearly related to the width of surface steps/gaps in strike-slip faults. For
 485 instance, they determine a 30% probability of rupture propagation across 5 km wide steps or gaps. In
 486 the same way, they also explore the influence of fault bends in rupture propagation and conclude that
 487 changes in strike have a significant role on rupture propagation when exceeding 25°. However, recent
 488 events suggest that those rules can be significantly overstepped, such as the 2016 M7.8 Kaikoura,
 489 New Zealand, earthquake during which the rupture jumped over large distances (10 to 20 km) from
 490 the Canterbury faults to the Marlborough faults. During this same event, some sections of the
 491 Canterbury surface ruptures intersect at orthogonal angle (Litchfield et al., 2018). Considering those
 492 empirical relationships, an ‘extreme’ scenario rupturing the whole Pallatanga fault system cannot be
 493 excluded, then mobilizing a rupture length larger than 150 km from tip (south of Pallatanga at the
 494 western margin of the Andes) to tip (few km northeast of Pisayambo at the eastern margin of the
 495 Andes). Such an event could also mobilize close reverse segment in the IAV, a combination of strike-
 496 slip and thrust segments having been observed during historical cases (see 2002 M7.9 Denali and
 497 2016 M7.8 Kaikoura events). In that case, our geological mapping is consistent with scenarios of
 498 large earthquakes of $M_w=7.5+$, accounting for surface rupture length of 150 km or Rupture area of
 499 4500 km² (Wells and Coppersmith, 1994). This estimation is coherent with that of the 1797
 500 Riobamba earthquake magnitude based on historical accounts (Beauval et al., 2010). Unfortunately,
 501 we do not have sufficiently continuous and reliable data to validate this statement based on the most
 502 recent earthquake surface rupture (two sites distant of 40 km, from Rumipamba to Igualata), or based
 503 on paleoseismological recordings (one trenched site in Rumipamba and one outcrop in Sicalpa at 10
 504 km, see Baize et al., 2015).

505 Keeping in mind the whole range of uncertainty and assuming a constant earthquake rate over time,
 506 the slip v time distribution at the Rumipamba site suggests that the fault behaviour is not perfectly
 507 periodic, but is better matched by a slip predictable model (Figure 12). The 1797 earthquake (E1)
 508 triggered too soon in a time predictable model. Additional data are needed to constrain this first
 509 appreciation, to understand if this is a common feature all along the Pallatanga fault. One first-choice
 510 site to explore is the Igualata summit, and another one is close to the pass between the Rio Pangor
 511 valley and the Cajabamba and Laguna Colta (site 2010-19, see Supplementary material).

512 We describe the fact that the Igualata, Huisla and Mulmul edifices, which activity period have been
 513 recently dated between ~380-100, ~600-500, and ~180-140 kyr, respectively (Bablon et al., 2019),
 514 are affected by the Pallatanga Fault, as well as many younger volcanic products filling the basin, such
 515 as the Guano lava flow and debris avalanche deposit from Chimborazo volcano. In terms of slip rate,
 516 our new data filled a gap of knowledge in the middle of the CCPP fault system between the south-
 517 westernmost CCPP section (the fault system crosses the littoral plain of Puna Island with minimal
 518 Holocene slip rate of 6–8 mm year (Dumont et al., 2005a; Dumont et al., 2005) and the northernmost

519 section (Holocene slip rates around 10 mm/yr according to Tibaldi et al. (2007) along the Chingual
 520 section). In Figure 13 and Table 1, we report the whole set of slip rate values estimated from both our
 521 field data and available datings or stratigraphic information. The Pallatanga fault is active at least
 522 since the beginning of the Iqualata volcano building (~350 kyr), and probably largely before if we
 523 assume a connection with the Puna fault in the Guayaquil gulf (Witt et al., 2006). We ranked the
 524 values of slip rates obtained in the previous section with respect to their reliability, roughly estimated
 525 based on the robustness of the age of displaced marker and the precision or accuracy of the piercing
 526 line. We consider the slip rate is reliable when the age is estimated for a dated marker (^{14}C or K-Ar)
 527 and when piercing line is geometrically well-constrained. Speculative clues are those for which none
 528 of those conditions are filled-in. In between, questionable cases bear rather reliable age or offset.
 529 Based on this, there could be an increase of slip rate around the Iqualata area, north of Rumipamba
 530 where slip rate estimate is reliable, and south of Pisayambo. This trend is mainly driven by two spots
 531 with questionable results both due to poorly constrained age of displaced deposits and could be
 532 revised with further data acquisition. Despite the deformation partitioning of slip from the Pallatanga
 533 – Rumipamba segments to the Pisayambo fault zone, on one hand, and the north-south folds on the
 534 other hand, there seems to be a variability of slip rate along strike. This two-fold change -from ~2-3
 535 mm/yr to ~4-6 mm/yr- occurs around the Iqualata volcano area over distances from 25 to 40 km
 536 (distances between available data). Therefore, the whole fault system would show changes at local
 537 (2-3 to 4-6 mm/yr) to regional (2 to 10 mm/yr) scales. Spatial changes are described both along long-
 538 living and segmented faults, like the 400 km-long Doruneh Fault in Iran (Farbod et al., 2016) or
 539 along young and evolving fault systems, like the Eastern California Shear Zone (Angster et al., 2018;
 540 Frankel et al., 2011; Kirby et al., 2008). In this latter case, variability is distributed over comparable
 541 along-strike distances as along the Pallatanga fault system. Along the ECSZ, the along-strike
 542 variation of strain is interpreted as the consequence of transfer to distributed structures off the fault of
 543 concern. This then suggests that this kind of variability could be a common trend of young and
 544 evolving fault systems, such as the Pallatanga Fault. Note that transfer of deformation back and forth
 545 and interaction between faults is also evoked to explain temporal changes at a single site (Gold et al.,
 546 2013).

547 Fault map, when overviewed at the regional scale, suggests that there are changing pattern from SW
 548 (Pallatanga area) to NE (Riobamba then Pelileo areas) with multiplication of fault sections, branches
 549 and parallel strands. Long-living crustal magmatic bodies are known to make more difficult the
 550 lateral propagation of faults because they modify the thermo-mechanical properties of the bedrock
 551 (Dumont et al., 2017). It has also been proposed that the presence of a volcano could preclude the
 552 rupture propagation during a single earthquake (Yagi et al., 2016). By analogy, one can suggest that
 553 the migration of magmatic centres from northern Ecuador to Riobamba region during the last ~600
 554 kyr (Bablon et al., 2019) might have perturbed the development of a unique and high strain fault
 555 across the IAV. Growth of the north-south trending active folds in the IAV is poorly constrained in
 556 time, though their onset is probably not older than several hundred of thousand years like the
 557 magmatic bodies intersecting the PF according to their immature morphology (Alvarado, 2012), and
 558 those features could be seen as the product of this interaction. This hypothesis will be test further.

559 **7 Conclusion**

560 The primary objective of this work is to contribute to seismic hazard analyses in providing a detailed
 561 description of available data on one major and emblematic fault zone in Ecuador to infer slip rates,
 562 timing of past earthquakes and their uncertainties. This compilation of existing and new data for
 563 defining new fault zones is a first attempt to help in building realistic fault models for future
 564 Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analyses in Ecuador, providing updated fault maps and related slip

565 rates. We are aware of the heterogeneity of the data and further studies will have to enrich the fault
 566 database in geology (mapping, trenching, drilling, dating) or geophysics (sub-surface profiling), as
 567 well as in geodesy (GNSS, InSAR) and seismology (near-fault monitoring, relocating clusters). This
 568 is one goal of the on-going LMI SVAN group, which has developed an ambitious program to
 569 investigate the crustal faults.

570 The scarcity of paleoseismological data in Ecuador clearly preclude developing a segmentation
 571 model of the Pallatanga fault system like along well-studied fault systems, such as the Wasatch Fault
 572 (DuRoss et al., 2016). Recent large earthquakes illustrate that multiple segment ruptures are not rare
 573 and that “out of expectation” scenarios with either kinematically/geometrical complex configurations
 574 (2010 M7 Darfield: Atzori et al., 2012; 2010 M7.2 El Mayor Cucapah: Fletcher et al., 2014) or
 575 distant segments without structural linkage at depth (2016 M7.8 Kaikoura: Hamling et al., 2017)
 576 could happen during large strike-slip events. Recent developments in Probabilistic Seismic Hazard
 577 Analysis now consider those complexities (Chartier et al., 2019) developed a method which allows
 578 relaxing the fault segmentation in a same fault system, and then calculating the rate of multiple fault
 579 section ruptures accounting for each fault section specific slip rate and geometry, and the possible
 580 multiple section rupture scenarios defined as input. Those scenarios could be sized based on simple
 581 geometrical rules. We could use the Biasi and Wesnousky (2016, 2017) empirical approach,
 582 estimating a likelihood of rupture propagation through high angle bend and large step-overs.

583 **8 Conflict of Interest**

584 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
 585 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

586 **9 Contribution to the Field Statement**

587 Earthquake hazard evaluation, as well as tectonic models, require a sound knowledge of the sources
 588 of major earthquakes. This region is prone to a consequential shaking and surface faulting hazard, as
 589 proved by the occurrence of large (magnitude larger than 7) historical earthquakes. However the
 590 sources of those threats to population and infrastructures are still poorly characterized and quantified.
 591 This contribution provides new information along an extended part of one of the main faults in the
 592 Central Andes of Ecuador. We base our analyses and interpretation on geological data, offering the
 593 opportunity to size the various identified earthquake sources. Throughout the Pallatanga fault system,
 594 surface faulting and deformation is distributed over several sections in a wide band of ~10 km. The
 595 fault sections that we were able to study accommodate significant fractions of the regional
 596 deformation budget (~1 to ~6 mm per year out of 8). Surprisingly, the fault system is capable to
 597 generate surface ruptures not only during large events (such as the 1797 magnitude > 7.5 Riobamba
 598 earthquake) but also during small magnitude ones (such as the 2010 magnitude 5 Pisayambo
 599 earthquake).

600 **10 Author Contributions**

601 SB, LA, AA, HJ, in the conception and design of the work; SB, LA, AA, HJ, PE, JC, in the
 602 acquisition, analysis and interpretation of the data; SB, LA, AA, MB, XQ, PS, JLP in the drafting the
 603 work or revising it critically.

604 **11 Funding**

605 Field work expenses have been funded by the “Laboratoire Mixte International Séismes et Volcans
606 des Andes du Nord” of “Institut pour la Recherche et le Développement” (LMI-SVAN), by the
607 “Agence Nationale pour la Recherche” project ANR-REMAKE (N°ANR-15-CE04-0004), and by
608 proper funds from the “Institut de Radioprotection et Sûreté Nucléaire”.

609 **12 Acknowledgments**

610 The Instituto Geofísico, Escuela Politécnica Nacional de Quito provided logistical help and scientific
611 support. The Envisat ASAR data were provided by European Space Agency through category-1
612 project 13248.

613 **13 Data Availability Statement**

614 The GIS-handled 4 m-resolution digital elevation model (DEM-4m) is from SigTierras of the
615 Ecuadorian Ministry of Agriculture, Quito (<http://ide.sigtierras.gob.ec/geoportal/>). The dataset
616 generated during the study is compiled in the Supplementary Material as a catalogue of localized
617 observations.

618

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- 791

792 **15 Tables**

793 **Table 1: Summary of slip rate along the 90-km section of the Pallatanga fault, based on observed offsets of landscape features and**
 794 **stratigraphic layers. Related uncertainties and reliability.**

Marker	D (km)	Offsets (m)	Time range (kyr)	SR min.	SR max	SR mean	Quality	Comment
Rumipamba, offset soils (Baize et al., 2015)	2	7.3-23	6.25 to 0	1.2	3	2.1	Very Reliable	Timing and offsets are well constrained
Rumipamba, offset of landscape features (Winter et al., 1993)	2	41.5	33 or 14 to 0 13 or 10 to 0*	1.3	3	2.1	Reliable	Questionable age of incision
				2.9	4.6	3.7	Questionable	Very hypothetical age of incision
Site A (deflected VAD incised valleys)	24	60-120	60 or 45 to 0 [#]	2.5 ^{\$}	4.2 ^{\$}	3.4 ^{\$}	Speculative	Age and amount of displacement are not constrained
Site B (deflected VAD incised valleys)	26	60-90	60 or 45 to 0	2.5 ^{\$}	3.5 ^{\$}	3 ^{\$}	Questionable	Age and amount of displacement are not well constrained
SW flank Iqualata volcano	28	900-1500	376 to 0	2.4	4	3.2*	Questionable	Age and amount of displacement are not well constrained
Iqualata volcano, incised gully	37	68-78	33 or 14 to 0	2.1	5.6	3.85	Reliable	Displacement is well constrained ; age is questionable
NE flank Iqualata	44	2100-2500	376 to 0	5.6	6.6	6.1	Questionable	Age and amount of displacement are not well constrained
Huisla VAD incised creek	55	60-	180 or 15 to 0	0.3	4	2.15	Speculative	Age and amount of displacement are not constrained
Pisayambo moraine (Champenois et al., 2017)	90	15-20	33 or 15 to 0	0.45	1.4	0.925	Questionable	Age and amount of displacement are not well constrained
Latacunga fold topography	90	N/A	InSAR	2	2.4	2.2	Reliable	Very short term assessment

795

796 SR: slip rate (mm/yr). Age of landforms according to Winter et al. (1993) * and Samaniego et al. (2012)[#]; [#]Slip rates includes apparent offset of ~110 m on parallel strand (Baize et al.,
 797 2015)

799 16 Figure captions

800 Figure 1. Location of the investigated area in its tectonic context. Upper left inset gives a general
 801 geodynamic overview illustrating the major role of the CCPP (Chingual Cosanga Pallatanga Puna)
 802 fault zone acting as a boundary between the South America Plate and the North Andean Block
 803 (NAB) in grey. The major active faults are the bold red lines; the investigated sectors are the
 804 Pallatanga fault south of Riobamba (R), the fault segments cutting the Igualata and Huisla volcanoes
 805 (IH) and the fault continuation around the Laguna Pisayambo (P) and the fault-related folds nearby
 806 Latacunga (L). (I) is Ibarra. The offshore bold line represents the subduction trench location, more
 807 than 100 km west of the Puna segment fault. G: Guayaquil; Q: Quito; ESB: Eastern Subandean Belt.

808 Figure 2: Illustration of the signature of an active portion of the Pallatanga fault on the 4 m resolution
 809 DEM and corresponding field panorama. On the left picture, one can observe one of the trenches dug
 810 in 2009-2010 and presented in Baize et al. (2015). The fault trace is easily inferred from an uphill-
 811 facing and counter-slope scarp, matching a deflection in perpendicular morphological features
 812 (channel incisions, ridges). See Figure 3 and Figure S8 in Supplementary Material for location.

813 Figure 3: Morphotectonic map resulting from the DEM and field work analyses. We define various
 814 categories of morphological lineaments: 1) Lineament with scarps are morphological features with a
 815 clear recent signature with a vertical separation of the ground surface in Quaternary deposits; 2)
 816 Strike-slip evidence are lineaments for which field (or rarely DEM) analysis has shown up the lateral
 817 displacement of a recent morphological feature; 3) Pressure ridge are elongated hills that disturb the
 818 local morphology, associated with deflection of morphological features; they are suspected to
 819 correspond to surface expression of transpressive pop-up structures due to strike-slip faulting at
 820 depth; 4) Folds are symmetrical and large-wavelength elongated disturbances of the ground surface
 821 and young sediments; 5) Fault-related flexures are asymmetrical disturbances of the surface revealing
 822 relative uplifting and subsiding blocks and then potentially corresponding to buried reverse faults.
 823 Flexure scarps are locally topped by to symmetrical folds in some places, potentially relating to a
 824 lateral component; 6) undistinguished lineaments inferred from DEM are suspected to relate to active
 825 faulting but without clear evidence of recent displacement; 7) inherited lineaments are clearly
 826 associated with basement structures (shear planes, bedding); gravitational scars are arcuate features
 827 associated with landslides mostly located in the deeply incised Patate and Chambo Rivers' valleys,
 828 some of them having been caused by the 1949 Pelileo earthquake (label Z). Labels A, X, Y refers to
 829 other features described in the text. The simplified geological map has been digitized from the
 830 National Geological Map of Ecuador (Longo and Baldock, 1982); volcano footprints are from
 831 Bernard and Andrade (2016). White boxes locate the zoom-in figures in this paper.

832 Figure 4: Zoom-in in the San Andres village area. The fault intersects the Pleistocene and Holocene
 833 volcanic deposits of the Riobamba basin. From the SW to the NE, we observe first a pressure ridge
 834 within the Chimborazo Avalanche Deposits (age poorly constrained, probably around 45 ky)
 835 collocated with a lateral deflection (60 to 120 m) of a incised channel (label A). Second, the San
 836 Andres valley, within which the 4 ky old Guano lava flow is emplaced, is also dextrally displaced
 837 (label B, 60 m). Finally, the fault trace is inferred by the bumps on top of the Guano lava flow before
 838 it cuts the Igualata volcano slopes, deflects incised streams and deforms Holocene soils (label C).

839 Figure 5. Zoom-in of the Iguayata center area. The figure highlights several sharp scarps and
 840 deflecting lineaments across the covered area, along the red arrows. The figure focuses on the
 841 lineament that includes the Figure 6 features and that seems to cause the 160 m right lateral
 842 deflection of the major incision.

843 Figure 6: Field observations along the main DEM lineament, which clearly corresponds to a
 844 cumulative uphill-facing counter scarp that offsets morphological features (a). A focus on the top of
 845 this scarp allows to document a fresh free face scarp (b) that is proposed to correspond to the last
 846 historical earthquake of the area (M7.6 1797 Riobamba earthquake); en echelon open fractures could
 847 be related to this event as well. Picture (c) nicely illustrates the successive right-lateral offsets of a
 848 small incision feature at the base of the cumulative scarp; those offsets seem too high to be associated
 849 with one single event and this could reveal the discontinuous incision of the feature as well.

850 Figure 7: Topographic map of the Iguayata edifice with hill-shade DEM picture and related elevation
 851 contours (contour spacing: 100 m; bold contour each 1000 m). Based on topographic profiles across
 852 the edifice (one profile is presented as an example with black arrows in the mean NW-SE direction),
 853 we traced the base of the edifice at the change in slope (yellow dashed line) and, assuming a rough
 854 cylindrical initial shape, we infer a right-lateral displacement of the whole volcano since its setup
 855 (1500 to 2100 m). Red lines are the morphotectonic lineaments forming the fault zone.

856 Figure 8: Illustration of the deformation of the Huisla volcano by the fault. (a) The map presents the
 857 course of the fault between red arrows, based on its morphological imprint. Southwest of the edifice,
 858 several drainage features (yellow dashed lines) are deflected; the fault cuts the southern flank of the
 859 Huisla edifice, then the Avalanche Debris of this volcano (emplaced between 215 ky and 175 ky
 860 based on stratigraphical relationships, according to Bablon et al., submitted) and landscape features;
 861 A and B labels locate sites described in the text. b) A road cut exposes the Huisla fault segment
 862 juxtaposing the Huisla Avalanche Debris (to the right) with interbedded colluvial and volcanic layers
 863 (Pleistocene?). c) Panoramic view from the south of the Huisla edifice, disrupted by the fault
 864 segment; grey lines depict the possible original slopes of the volcano, before its partial collapse and
 865 succeeding incision. P. R.: Patate River.

866 Figure 9: a) The Pisayambo Fault segment has ruptured during a small magnitude event ($M_w \sim 5$) in
 867 2010, leaving a 9-km long surface rupture (Champenois et al., 2017). b) and c) This coseismic
 868 surface rupture, with clear right-lateral offsets (up to 30-40 cm), occurred along a right-lateral
 869 cumulative fault which is clearly marked in topography with a scarp and offset of landscape features
 870 (such as moraine cordon).

871 Figure 10: North of the strike-slip fault sections in the Inter-Andean Valley, the fault-related folds
 872 and flexures around Ambato and Latacunga cities are clearly exposed in topography. A-B illustrates a
 873 topographic profile across those fault-related folds and flexures, suggesting a reverse component
 874 along near surface dip slip faults. Reverse faults have been observed in places between Quaternary
 875 volcanic deposits (e.g. between the Chalupas ignimbrite, 215 kyr old according to Bablon et al.,
 876 2018, and the Latacunga series) and some symmetrical folds (e.g. Yambo laguna) clearly impact the
 877 landscape development.

878 Figure 11: Illustration of surface deformation in the Inter-Andean Valley seen by SAR geodesy. The
 879 gentle decrease in the Line-Of-Sight displacement rate towards the east (due to the interseismic
 880 loading because of the subduction convergence) is affected by two sharper gradients in displacement
 881 rate that could match with the two IAV-bounding fault zones (Alvarado, 2012) that cause the uplift

882 of the Cordilleras. Posing several assumptions (see text), we estimate that the fault slip rates could
883 reach 1.7 mm/yr and 0.5 mm/yr for the Eastern and Western Boundary Faults, respectively.

884 Figure 12: Illustration of the slip versus time history inferred from the Rumipamba trench results.
885 (A): X-axis is calibrated date; black bell-shaped curves are probability density functions of
886 earthquake dates resulting from the stratigraphic model and the resulting Bayesian estimation of
887 dates determined by OxCal online tool. Grey shaded boxes depict the uncertainty ranges of
888 paleoearthquakes including age uncertainty (from OxCal model) and slip range (from possible slip
889 vector range). The staircase curve represents a ‘mean’ slip versus date scenario based on those
890 results, representing three earthquake cycles. A value of paleoseismological slip rate is extracted
891 from this curve, depending on the initial slip vector hypothesis. (B): The ‘mean’ slip versus data
892 scenario (staircase curve) (Figure 12) is presented to illustrate that the Rumipamba better matches a
893 slip-predictable model.

894 Figure 13: Synthesis of slip rate estimation along the section of the 90-km Pallatanga fault system of
895 concern. This graph is based on observed offsets of landscape features and stratigraphic layers, and
896 related uncertainties and reliability, reported in Table 1.